

More On P-Union and P-Intersection of Neutrosophic Soft Cubic Set

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Abstract: The P-union, P-intersection, P-OR and P-AND of neutrosophic soft cubic sets are introduced and their related properties are investigated. We show that the P-union and the P-intersection of two internal neutrosophic soft cubic sets are also internal neutrosophic soft cubic sets. The conditions for the P-union (P-intersection) of two T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets is also dealt with.

We provide conditions for the P-union (P-intersection) of two T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-internal (resp. I- internal, F- internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets. Further the conditions for the P-union (resp. P-intersection) of two neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be both T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets and T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets are also framed.

Keywords: Cubic set, Neutrosophic cubic set, Neutrosophic soft cubic set, T-internal (resp. I- internal, F- internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets , T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic set.

1 Introduction

Florentine Smarandache [10,11] coined neutrosophic sets and neutrosophic logic which extends the concept of the classical sets, fuzzy sets and its extensions. In neutrosophic set, indeterminacy is quantified explicitly and truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity – membership are independent. This assumption is very important in many applications such as information fusion in which we try to combine the data from different sensors. Pabita Kumar Majii [18] had combined the Neutrosophic set with soft sets and introduced a new mathematical model ‘ Neutrosophic soft set’. Y. B. Jun et al [2], introduced a new notion, called a cubic set by using a fuzzy set and an interval-valued fuzzy set, and investigated several properties. Jun et al. [19] extended the concept of cubic sets to the neutrosophic cubic sets. [1] introduced neutrosophic soft cubic set and the notion of truth-internal (indeterminacy-internal, falsity-internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets and truth-external (indeterminacy-internal, falsity-internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets

As a continuation of the paper [1] We show that the P-union and the P-intersection of T-internal (resp. I- internal, F-internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets are also T-internal (resp. I-internal, F-internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets. We also provide conditions for the P-union (P-intersection) of two T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets.

We provide conditions for the P-union (P-intersection) of two T-external (resp. I- external, F- external)

neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-internal (resp. I- internal, F- internal) neutrosophic soft cubic sets.

We provide conditions for the P-union (resp. P-intersection) of two NSCS to be both T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets and T-external (resp. I- external, F- external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Definition: [5] Let E be a universe. Then a fuzzy set μ over E is defined by $X = \{ \mu_x(x) / x : x \in E \}$ where μ_x is called membership function of X and defined by $\mu_x : E \rightarrow [0,1]$. For each $x \in E$, the value $\mu_x(x)$ represents the degree of x belonging to the fuzzy set X.

2.2 Definition: [2] Let X be a non-empty set. By a cubic set, we mean a structure $\Xi = \{ \langle x, A(x), \mu(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$

in which A is an interval valued fuzzy set (IVF) and μ is a fuzzy set. It is denoted by $\langle A, \mu \rangle$.

2.3 Definition: [9] Let U be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Consider $A \subset E$. Let $P(U)$ denotes the set of all neutrosophic sets of U. The collection (F, A) is termed to be the soft neutrosophic set over U, where F is a mapping given by $F : A \rightarrow P(U)$.

2.4 Definition : [4] Let X be an universe. Then a neutrosophic (NS) set λ is an object having the form

$$\lambda = \{ \langle x : T(x), I(x), F(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]0, 1+[$ defines respectively the degree of Truth, the degree of

indeterminacy, and the degree of Falsehood of the element $x \in X$ to the set λ with the condition.

$$0 \leq T(x) + I(x) + F(x) \leq 3^+$$

2.5 Definition : [7] Let X be a non-empty set. An interval neutrosophic set (INS) A in X is characterized by the truth-membership function A_T , the indeterminacy-membership function A_I and the falsity-membership function A_F . For each point $x \in X$, $A_T(x), A_I(x), A_F(x) \subseteq [0,1]$.

For two INS

$$A = \{ \langle x, [A_T^-(x), A_T^+(x)], [A_I^-(x), A_I^+(x)], [A_F^-(x), A_F^+(x)] \rangle : x \in X \}$$

and

$$B = \{ \langle x, [B_T^-(x), B_T^+(x)], [B_I^-(x), B_I^+(x)], [B_F^-(x), B_F^+(x)] \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Then,

1. $A \subseteq B$ if and only if

$$A_T^-(x) \leq B_T^-(x), A_T^+(x) \leq B_T^+(x)$$

$$A_I^-(x) \geq B_I^-(x), A_I^+(x) \geq B_I^+(x)$$

$$A_F^-(x) \geq B_F^-(x), A_F^+(x) \geq B_F^+(x) \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

2. $A = B$ if and only if

$$A_T^-(x) = B_T^-(x), A_T^+(x) = B_T^+(x)$$

$$A_I^-(x) = B_I^-(x), A_I^+(x) = B_I^+(x)$$

$$A_F^-(x) = B_F^-(x), A_F^+(x) = B_F^+(x) \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

3. $A^{\tilde{c}} = \{ \langle x, [A_I^-(x), A_I^+(x)], [A_T^-(x), A_T^+(x)], [A_F^-(x), A_F^+(x)] \rangle : x \in X \}$

4. $A \tilde{\cap} B = \{ \langle x, [\min\{A_T^-(x), B_T^-(x)\}, \min\{A_T^+(x), B_T^+(x)\}],$

$$[\max\{A_I^-(x), B_I^-(x)\}, \max\{A_I^+(x), B_I^+(x)\}],$$

$$[\max\{A_F^-(x), B_F^-(x)\}, \max\{A_F^+(x), B_F^+(x)\}] \rangle : x \in X \}$$

5.

$$A \tilde{\cup} B = \{ \langle x, [\max\{A_T^-(x), B_T^-(x)\}, \max\{A_T^+(x), B_T^+(x)\}],$$

$$[\min\{A_I^-(x), B_I^-(x)\}, \min\{A_I^+(x), B_I^+(x)\}],$$

$$[\min\{A_F^-(x), B_F^-(x)\}, \min\{A_F^+(x), B_F^+(x)\}] \rangle : x \in X \}$$

2.6 Definition: [1]

Let U be an initial universe set. Let $NC(U)$ denote the set of all neutrosophic cubic sets and E be the set of parameters. Let $A \subset E$ then

$$(P, A) = \{ P(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in U \} \mid e_i \in A \subset E \}$$

where $A_{e_i}(x) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}^T(x), A_{e_i}^I(x), A_{e_i}^F(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$ is an interval neutrosophic set,

$$\lambda_{e_i}(x) = \{ \langle x, \lambda_{e_i}^T(x), \lambda_{e_i}^I(x), \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$$
 is a neutrosophic set. The pair (P, A) is termed to be the

neutrosophic soft cubic set over U where P is a mapping given by $P : A \rightarrow NC(U)$.

2.7 Definition: [1]

Let X be an initial universe set. A neutrosophic soft cubic set (P, A) in X is said to be

- truth-internal (briefly, T-internal) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)), \quad (2.1)$$

- indeterminacy-internal (briefly, I-internal) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)), \quad (2.2)$$

- falsity-internal (briefly, F-internal) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)). \quad (2.3)$$

If a neutrosophic soft cubic set in X satisfies (2.1), (2.2) and (2.3) we say that (P, A) is an internal neutrosophic soft cubic set in X .

2.8 Definition: [1]

Let X be an initial universe set. A neutrosophic soft cubic set (P, A) in X is said to be

- truth-external (briefly, T-external) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x))), \quad (2.4)$$

- indeterminacy-external (briefly, I-external) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x))), \quad (2.5)$$

- falsity-external (briefly, F-external) if the following inequality is valid

$$(\forall x \in X, e_i \in E) (\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x))). \quad (2.6)$$

If a neutrosophic soft cubic set (P, A) in X satisfies (2.4), (2.5) and (2.6), we say that (P, A) is an external neutrosophic soft cubic set in X .

2.9 Definition [1]

Let

$$(P, I) = \{ P(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

and

$$(Q, J) = \{ Q(e_i) = B_i = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

be two neutrosophic soft cubic sets in X . Let I and J be any two subsets of E (set of parameters), then we have the following

1. $(P, I) = (Q, J)$ if and only if the following conditions are satisfied

a) $I = J$ and

- b) $P(e_i)=Q(e_i)$ for all $e_i \in I$ if and only if $A_{e_i}(x)=B_{e_i}(x)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}(x)=\mu_{e_i}(x)$ for all $x \in X$ corresponding to each $e_i \in I$.
- 2. (P,I) and (Q,J) are two neutrosophic soft cubic set then we define and denote P-order as $(P,I) \subseteq_P (Q,J)$ if and only if the following conditions are satisfied
 - c) $I \subseteq J$ and
 - d) $P(e_i) \leq_P Q(e_i)$ for all $e_i \in I$ if and only if $A_{e_i}(x) \subseteq B_{e_i}(x)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}(x)$ for all $x \in X$ corresponding to each $e_i \in I$.
- 3. (P,I) and (Q,J) are two neutrosophic soft cubic set then we define and denote P- order as $(P,I) \subseteq_R (Q,J)$ if and only if the following conditions are satisfied
 - e) $I \subseteq J$ and
 - f) $P(e_i) \leq_R Q(e_i)$ for all $e_i \in I$ if and only if $A_{e_i}(x) \subseteq B_{e_i}(x)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}(x) \geq \mu_{e_i}(x)$ for all $x \in X$ corresponding to each $e_i \in I$.

2.10 Definition: [1]

Let (F,I) and (G,J) be two neutrosophic soft cubic sets (NSCS) in X where I and J are any two subsets of the parametric set E . Then we define P-union of neutrosophic soft cubic set as $(F,I) \cup_P (G,J) = (H,C)$ where $C = I \cup J$

$$H(e_i) = \begin{cases} F(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J \end{cases}$$

where $F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J$$

where $A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)$ represent interval neutrosophic sets.

Hence

$$F^T(e_i) \vee_P G^T(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J,$$

$$F^I(e_i) \vee_P G^I(e_i) =$$

$$\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^I(x), B_{e_i}^I(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J,$$

$$F^F(e_i) \vee_P G^F(e_i) =$$

$$\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^F(x), B_{e_i}^F(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J.$$

2.11 Definition: [1]

Let (F, I) and (G, J) be two neutrosophic soft cubic sets (NSCS) in X where I and J are any subsets of parameter's set E .

Then we define P-intersection of neutrosophic soft cubic set as $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $C = I \cap J$,

$$H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i)$$

$$H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i) \quad \text{and} \quad e_i \in I \cap J. \text{ Here}$$

$F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \wedge \mu_{e_i})(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J$$

where $A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)$ represent interval neutrosophic sets.

Hence

$$F^T(e_i) \wedge_P G^T(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J,$$

$$F^I(e_i) \wedge_P G^I(e_i) =$$

$$\{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}^I(x), B_{e_i}^I(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^I \wedge \mu_{e_i}^I)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J,$$

$$F^F(e_i) \wedge_P G^F(e_i) =$$

$$\{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}^F(x), B_{e_i}^F(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^F \wedge \mu_{e_i}^F)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \cap J$$

3 More On P-union And P-intersection Of Neutrosophic Soft Cubic Set

Defintion: 3.1

Let

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in I \} \text{ and}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad e_i \in J \}$$

be neutrosophic soft cubic set (NSCS) in X . Then

- [1] P-OR is denoted by $(F, I) \vee_P (G, J)$ and de-

defined as $(F, I) \vee_P (G, J) = (H, I \times J)$ where

$$H(\alpha_i, \beta_i) = F(\alpha_i) \cup_P G(\beta_i) \quad \text{for all } (\alpha_i, \beta_i) \in I \times J.$$

- [2] P-AND is denoted by $(F, I) \wedge_P (G, J)$ and de-

defined as $(F, I) \wedge_P (G, J) = (H, I \times J)$ where

$$H(\alpha_i, \beta_i) = F(\alpha_i) \cap_P G(\beta_i) \quad \text{for all } (\alpha_i, \beta_i) \in I \times J.$$

Example: 3.2

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ be initial universe and $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$ parameter's set. Let (F, I) be a neutrosophic soft cubic set over X and defined as $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$ and

X	F(e ₁)		F(e ₂)	
	$\langle Ae_1(x), \lambda_{e_1}(x) \rangle$		$\langle Ae_2(x), \lambda_{e_2}(x) \rangle$	
x ₁	[0.5,0.6][0.6,0.7][0.5,0.6]	[0.4,0.5][0.6,0.6]	[0.3,0.6][0.2,0.7][0.2,0.4]	[0.3,0.4][0.4,0.4]
x ₂	[0.4,0.5][0.7,0.8][0.2,0.3]	[0.5,0.6][0.6,0.6]	[0.3,0.5][0.6,0.8][0.2,0.6]	[0.4,0.7][0.5,0.5]
x ₃	[0.2,0.3][0.2,0.3][0.3,0.5]	[0.3,0.4][0.6,0.6]	[0.4,0.7][0.2,0.5][0.3,0.6]	[0.5,0.6][0.6,0.6]

$$(G, J) = \{G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J\}$$

X	G(e ₁)		G(e ₂)	
	$\langle Be_1(x), \mu_{e_1}(x) \rangle$		$\langle Ae_2(x), \mu_{e_2}(x) \rangle$	
x ₁	[0.7,0.9][0.3,0.5][0.3,0.4]	[0.7,0.4][0.6,0.6]	[0.4,0.7][0.1,0.3][0.1,0.2]	[0.5,0.2][0.2,0.2]
x ₂	[0.5,0.6][0.3,0.7][0.1,0.2]	[0.6,0.4][0.2,0.2]	[0.4,0.6][0.4,0.7][0.2,0.5]	[0.6,0.5][0.4,0.4]
x ₃	[0.3,0.4][0.1,0.2][0.2,0.4]	[0.5,0.3][0.5,0.5]	[0.5,0.8][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.4]	[0.7,0.3][0.4,0.4]

P-OR is denoted by $(H, I \times J) = (F, I) \vee_P (G, J)$

where

$I \times J = \{(e_1, e_1), (e_1, e_2), (e_2, e_1), (e_2, e_2)\}$ is defined

X	H(e ₁ ,e ₁)		H(e ₁ ,e ₂)		H(e ₂ ,e ₁)		H(e ₂ ,e ₂)	
	F(e ₁) U G(e ₁)		F(e ₁) U G(e ₂)		F(e ₂) U G(e ₁)		F(e ₂) U G(e ₂)	
x ₁	[0.7,0.9][0.6,0.7][0.5,0.6]	[0.7,0.5][0.6,0.6]	[0.5,0.6][0.6,0.6]	[0.5,0.5][0.6,0.6]	[0.7,0.9][0.3,0.5][0.3,0.4]	[0.7,0.4][0.6,0.6]	[0.4,0.7][0.1,0.3][0.1,0.2]	[0.5,0.2][0.2,0.2]
x ₂	[0.5,0.6][0.7,0.8][0.2,0.3]	[0.6,0.6][0.6,0.6]	[0.4,0.6][0.7,0.8][0.2,0.6]	[0.6,0.6][0.6,0.6]	[0.4,0.6][0.4,0.7][0.2,0.5]	[0.6,0.5][0.4,0.4]	[0.4,0.6][0.4,0.7][0.2,0.5]	[0.6,0.5][0.4,0.4]
x ₃	[0.3,0.4][0.2,0.3][0.3,0.5]	[0.5,0.3][0.5,0.5]	[0.5,0.8][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.4]	[0.5,0.8][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.4]	[0.5,0.8][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.4]	[0.7,0.3][0.4,0.4]	[0.5,0.8][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.4]	[0.7,0.3][0.4,0.4]

Definition:3.3

The complement of a neutrosophic soft cubic set

$$(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$$

denoted by $(F, I)^C$ and defined as

$$(F, I)^C = \{(F, I)^C = (F^C, -I)\}, \text{ where } F^C : -I \rightarrow NC(X)$$

and

$$F^C(e_i) = (F(-e_i))^C \text{ for all } e_i \in -I$$

$$= (F(e_i))^C \text{ (as } -(-e_i) = e_i)$$

$$(F, I)^C = \{(F(e_i))^C = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}^C(x), \lambda_{e_i}^C(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$$

$$(F, I)^C = \{ \langle x, (1 - A_{e_i}^{+T}, 1 - A_{e_i}^{-T}), [1 - A_{e_i}^{+I}, 1 - A_{e_i}^{-I}], [1 - A_{e_i}^{+F}, 1 - A_{e_i}^{-F}] \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I$$

Example:3.4

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$ be initial universe and $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$ parameter's set. Let (F, I) be a neutrosophic soft cubic set over X and defined as $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$

X	F(e ₁)		F(e ₂)	
	$\langle Ae_1(x), \lambda_{e_1}(x) \rangle$		$\langle Ae_2(x), \lambda_{e_2}(x) \rangle$	
x ₁	[0.3,0.5][0.1,0.4][0.5,0.8]	[0.6,0.5][0.7]	[0.4,0.6][0.5,0.7][0.6,0.9]	[0.5,0.4][0.4,0.4]
x ₂	[0.6,0.8][0.4,0.7][0.4,0.7]	[0.7,0.5][0.3]	[0.2,0.4][0.4,0.7][0.3,0.6]	[0.3,0.7][0.8]

Then

$$(F, I)^C = \{(F(e_i))^C = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}^C(x), \lambda_{e_i}^C(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$$

is defined as.

X	F ^c (e ₁)		F ^c (e ₂)	
	$\langle A^c_{e_1}(x), \lambda^c_{e_1}(x) \rangle$		$\langle A^c_{e_2}(x), \lambda^c_{e_2}(x) \rangle$	
x ₁	[0.5,0.7][0.6,0.9][0.2,0.5]	[0.4,0.5][0.3]	[0.4,0.6][0.3,0.5][0.1,0.4]	[0.5,0.6][0.6,0.6]
x ₂	[0.2,0.4][0.3,0.6][0.3,0.6]	[0.3,0.5][0.7]	[0.6,0.8][0.3,0.6][0.4,0.7]	[0.7,0.3][0.2]

Proposition :3.5

Let X be initial universe and I, J, L and S subsets of parametric set E . Then for any neutrosophic soft cubic sets $\mathcal{A} = (F, I), \mathcal{B} = (G, J), \mathcal{C} = (E, L), \mathcal{D} = (T, S)$ the following properties hold

- (1) if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq_P \mathcal{C}$ then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{C}$.
- (2) if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ then $\mathcal{B}^C \subseteq_P \mathcal{A}^C$.
- (3) if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{C}$ then $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B} \cap_P \mathcal{C}$.
- (4) if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{C} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ then $\mathcal{A} \cup_P \mathcal{C} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$.
- (5) if $\mathcal{A} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{C} \subseteq_P \mathcal{D}$ then $\mathcal{A} \cup_P \mathcal{C} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B} \cup_P \mathcal{D}$ and $\mathcal{A} \cap_P \mathcal{C} \subseteq_P \mathcal{B} \cap_P \mathcal{D}$.

Proof: Proof is straight forward

Theorem:3.6 Let (F, I) be a neutrosophic soft cubic set over X .

- (1) If (F, I) is an internal neutrosophic soft cubic set, then $(F, I)^C$ is also an internal neutrosophic soft cubic set (INSCS).
- (2) If (F, I) is an external neutrosophic soft cubic set, then $(F, I)^C$ is also an external Neutrosophic soft cubic set (ENSCS).

Proof.

(1) Given

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

is an INSCS this implies

$$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$$

$$A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x),$$

$$A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x),$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

this implies

$$1 - A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-T}(x),$$

$$1 - A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-I}(x),$$

$$1 - A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Hence $(F, I)^c$ is an INSCS.

(2) Given

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

is an ENSCS this implies

$$\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)),$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x))$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x))$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Since $\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x))$ &

$$0 \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq 1,$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)) \quad \&$$

$$0 \leq A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq 1,$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)) \quad \&$$

$$0 \leq A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq 1$$

So we have

$$\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \text{ or } A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x),$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \text{ or } A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x),$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \text{ or } A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x)$$

this implies

$$1 - \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \geq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \text{ or } 1 - A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \geq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^T(x),$$

$$1 - \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \geq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \text{ or } 1 - A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \geq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^I(x),$$

$$1 - \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \geq 1 - A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \text{ or } 1 - A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \geq 1 - \lambda_{e_i}^F(x),$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Thus $1 - \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (1 - A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), 1 - A_{e_i}^{+T}(x))$,

$$1 - \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (1 - A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), 1 - A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)),$$

$$1 - \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (1 - A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), 1 - A_{e_i}^{+F}(x))$$

Hence (F, I) is an ENSCS.

Theorem: 3.7

Let

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

and

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

be internal neutrosophic cubic soft sets. Then,

(1) $(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS

(2) $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS

Proof:

(1) Since (F, I) and (G, J) are internal neutrosophic soft cubic sets. So for (F, I) we have

$$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$$

$$A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), \quad A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Also for (G, J) we $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$

$$B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x), \quad B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then we have

$$\max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\},$$

$$\max\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\},$$

$$\max\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\},$$

for all $e_i \in I \cup J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Now by definition of P-union of (F, I) and (G, J) , we have

$$(F, I) \cup_p (G, J) = (H, C) \text{ where } I \cup J = C \text{ and}$$

$$H(e_i) = \begin{cases} F(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J \end{cases}$$

if $e_i \in I \cap J$, then $F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i) = H(e_i) =$$

$$\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}.$$

where

$$F^T(e_i) \vee_p G^T(e_i) = \left\langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})^T(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\rangle,$$

$$F^I(e_i) \vee_p G^I(e_i) = \left\langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^I(x), B_{e_i}^I(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})^I(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\rangle,$$

$$F^F(e_i) \vee_p G^F(e_i) = \left\langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^F(x), B_{e_i}^F(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})^F(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\rangle.$$

Thus $(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS if $e_i \in I \cap J$.

If $e_i \in I - J$ or $e_i \in J - I$ then the result is trivial.

Hence $(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS in all cases.

(2) Since $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $I \cap J = C$

and $H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_p G(e_i)$. If

$e_i \in I \cap J$ then $F(e_i) \wedge_p G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_p G(e_i) = \left\langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \wedge \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\rangle.$$

Also given that (F, I) and (G, J) are INSCS.

So far we have

$$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x),$$

$$A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

And for (G, J) we have $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$

$$B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$.

$$\min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\},$$

$$\min\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^I \wedge \mu_{e_i}^I)(x) \leq \min\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\}$$

$$\min\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\} \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^F \wedge \mu_{e_i}^F)(x) \leq \min\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\}$$

for all $e_i \in I \cap J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Hence $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS.

Definition: 3.8

Given two neutrosophic soft cubic sets (NSCS)

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in J \},$$

if we interchange λ and μ ,

Then the new neutrosophic soft cubic set (NSCS) are denoted and defined as

$$(F, I)^* = \{ F(e_i) = \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in I \}$$

and $(G, J)^* = \{ G(e_i) = \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in J \}$ respectively.

Theorem 3.9

For two ENSCSs

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in J \}$$

in X , if $(F, I)^*$ and $(G, J)^*$ are INSCS in X then

$(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is an INSCS in X .

Proof:

Since

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in J \}$$

are ENSCS.

Then for (F, I) we have $\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)),$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)), \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x))$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$ and (G, J) we have

$$\mu_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)), \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)),$$

$$\mu_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x))$$

for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Also given that

$$(F, I)^* = \{ F(e_i) = \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J)^* = \{ G(e_i) = \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \mid e_i \in J \}$$

are INSCS so this implies $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$

$$A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$. And

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x).$$

for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Since (F, I) and (G, J)

are ENSCS and $(F, I)^*$ and $(G, J)^*$ are INSCS. Thus by definition of ENSCS and INSCS all the possibilities are under

1) (a1) $\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$

(a2) $\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$

(a3) $\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$

(b1) $\mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$

- (b2) $\mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$
- (b3) $\mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$
- 2) (a1) $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x)$
- (a2) $A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x)$
- (a3) $A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x)$
- (b1) $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x)$
- (b2) $B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x)$
- (b3) $B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x)$
- 3) (a1) $\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$
- (a2) $\lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$
- (a3) $\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$
- (b1) $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x)$
- (b2) $B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x)$
- (b3) $B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x)$
- 4) (a2) $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x)$
- (a2) $A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x)$
- (a2) $A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x)$
- (b1) $\mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$
- (b2) $\mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$
- (b2) $\mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)$

Since P-union of (F,I) and (G,J) is denoted and defined as $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $I \cup J = C$ and

$$H(e_i) = \begin{cases} F(e_i) & \text{if } e \in I - J \\ G(e_i) & \text{if } e \in J - I \\ F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) & \text{if } e \in I \cap J \end{cases}$$

if $e_i \in I \cap J$, then $F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ < x, \max\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}$$

where

$$F^T(e_i) \vee_P G^T(e_i) = \{ < x, \max\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}$$

$$F^I(e_i) \vee_P G^I(e_i) = \{ < x, \max\{A_{e_i}^I(x), B_{e_i}^I(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}$$

$$F^F(e_i) \vee_P G^F(e_i) = \{ < x, \max\{A_{e_i}^F(x), B_{e_i}^F(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}$$

for all $e_i \in I \cap J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Case: 1

If $H(e_i) = F(e_i)$ that is if $e_i \in I - J$

then from (1)(a1) and (2)(a1), we have

$$\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \text{ and } \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) = A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Thus

$$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$$

for all $e_i \in I - J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Similarly we can prove for (1)(a2), (2)(a2) and (1)(a3), (2)(a3).

Thus $A_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$ and

$$A_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+F}(x),$$

for all $e_i \in I - J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Case: 2

If $H(e_i) = G(e_i)$ that is if $e_i \in J - I$ then from (1)(b1) and (2)(b1), we have

$$\mu_{e_i}^T(x) = B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \text{ and } \mu_{e_i}^I(x) = B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$. Thus

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x),$$

for all $e_i \in J - I$ and for all $x \in X$. Similarly we can prove for (1)(b2) and (2)(b2) and (1)(b3) and (2)(b3). Thus

$$B_{e_i}^{-I}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+I}(x) \text{ and}$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-F}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^F(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+F}(x),$$

for all $e_i \in J - I$ and for all $x \in X$.

Case: 3

If $H(e_i) = F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i)$ that is if $e_i \in I \cap J$, then

from (1)(a1) and (1)(b1), we have

$$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ for all } e_i \in I \text{ and for all } x \in X.$$

and

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq \mu_{e_i}^T(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ for all } e_i \in J \text{ and for all } x \in X.$$

Hence (i)
 $e_i \in I \cap J$ then

$$\max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\} \leq \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\}.$$

Similarly we can prove (1)(a2) , (1)(b2) and (1)(a3), (1)(b3) .

Thus

$$\max\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\} \leq \left(\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I \right)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\}$$

$$, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\} \leq \left(\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F \right)(x) \leq \max\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\}$$

Thus in all the three cases $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J)$ is an INSCS in X .

Theorem: 3.10

For two ENSCSs

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

in X if

$$(F, I)^* = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J)^* = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

are INSCS in X then $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is an INSCS in X .

Proof: By similar way to Theorem 3.9 we can obtain the result.

Theorem: 3.11

Let

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

be ENSCSs in X such that

$$(F, I)^* = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J)^* = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$$

be ENSCS in X . Then P -union of (F, I) and (G, J) is an ENSCS in X .

Proof:

Since (F, I) , (G, J) , $(F, I)^*$ and $(G, J)^*$ are ENSCS so by definition of an external soft cubic set for (F, I) ,

(G, J) , $(F, I)^*$ and $(G, J)^*$ we have

$$\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)) \quad , \quad \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)) \quad ,$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x)) \quad ,$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

$$\mu_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)) \quad , \quad \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)) \quad ,$$

$$\mu_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)) \quad \text{for all } e_i \in J \text{ and for all } x \in X.$$

$$\mu_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)) \quad , \quad \mu_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), A_{e_i}^{+I}(x)) \quad ,$$

$$\mu_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), A_{e_i}^{+F}(x))$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $x \in X$.

$$\lambda_{e_i}^T(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)) \quad , \quad \lambda_{e_i}^I(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)) \quad ,$$

$$\lambda_{e_i}^F(x) \notin (B_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)) \quad \text{for all } e_i \in J \text{ and for all } x \in X$$

respectively.

Thus we have

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \notin \{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}$$

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I \right)(x) \notin \{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\} \}$$

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F \right)(x) \notin \{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\} \}$$

for all $e_i \in I \cap J$ and for all $x \in X$. Thus we have

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i} \right)(x) \notin \max\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}$$

for all $e_i \in I \cap J$ and for all $x \in X$. Also since

$$(F, I) \cup_P (G, J) = (H, C) \text{ where } I \cup J = C \text{ and}$$

$$H(e_i) = \begin{cases} F(e_i) & \text{if } e \in I - J \\ G(e_i) & \text{if } e \in J - I \\ F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) & \text{if } e \in I \cap J \end{cases}$$

if $e \in I \cap J$, then $F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \vee_P G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}.$$

where

$$F^T(e_i) \vee_P G^T(e_i) = \left\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x)\}, \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\}$$

$$F^I(e_i) \vee_P G^I(e_i) = \left\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^I(x), B_{e_i}^I(x)\}, \left(\lambda_{e_i}^I \vee \mu_{e_i}^I \right)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\}$$

$$F^F(e_i) \vee_p G^F(e_i) = \left\{ \langle x, \max\{A_{e_i}^F(x), B_{e_i}^F(x)\}, \left(\lambda_{e_i}^F \vee \mu_{e_i}^F \right)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \right\}$$

By definition of an external soft cubic set $(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is an ENSCS in X.

Example: 3.12

Let (P, I) and (Q, J) be neutrosophic soft cubic sets in X where

$$(P, I) = P(e_1) = \{ \langle x, ([0.3, 0.5] \cup [0.2, 0.5] \cup [0.5, 0.7]), (0.8, 0.3, 0.4) \rangle : e_1 \in I \}$$

$$(Q, J) = Q(e_1) = \{ \langle x, ([0.7, 0.9] \cup [0.6, 0.8] \cup [0.4, 0.7]), (0.4, 0.7, 0.3) \rangle : e_1 \in J \}$$

for all $x \in X$

Then (P, I) and (Q, J) are T-external neutrosophic cubic sets in X and $(P, I) \cap_p (Q, J) =$

$$(P, I) \cap (Q, J) = P \cap Q(e_1) = \{ \langle x, ([0.3, 0.5] \cup [0.2, 0.5] \cup [0.4, 0.7]), (0.4, 0.3, 0.3) \rangle : e_1 \in I \cap J \}$$

for all $x \in X$. $(P, I) \cap_p (Q, J)$ is not an T-external neutrosophic cubic set since

$$\left(\lambda_{e_1}^T \wedge \mu_{e_1}^T \right)(x) = \left(\lambda_{e_1}^T \cap \mu_{e_1}^T \right)(x) = 0.4 \in (0.3, 0.5)$$

From the above example it is clear that P-intersection of T-external neutrosophic soft cubic sets may not be an T-external neutrosophic soft cubic set. We provide a condition for the P-intersection of T-external (resp. I-external and F-external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-external (resp. I-external and F-external) neutrosophic soft cubic set.

Theorem: 3.13

Let

$$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in I \}$$

$$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in J \}$$

be T- ENSCSs in X such that

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \in \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}, \\ \min\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \} \end{array} \right\} \quad (3.7)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$.

Then $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is also an T- ENSCS.

Proof

Consider $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $I \cap J = C$

where $H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_p G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \wedge_p G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \wedge \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \}.$$

For each $e \in I \cap J$,

Take

$$\alpha_{e_i}^T = \min\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}$$

$$\text{and } \beta_{e_i}^T = \max\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}$$

Then $\alpha_{e_i}^T$ is one of $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$.

Now we consider $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ or $A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ only, as the remaining cases are similar to this one.

If $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ and so } \beta_{e_i}^T = B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$$

$$\text{thus } B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x) \leq (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x) =$$

$$B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = \beta_{e_i}^T < \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x).$$

$$\text{Hence } \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \notin \left((A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x) \right)$$

If $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, then $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$

and so $\beta_{e_i}^T = \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}$.

Assume that $\beta_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) <$

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x).$$

So from this we can write $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) <$

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ or}$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x).$$

For this case $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) <$

$A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ it is contradiction to the fact that (F, I) and (G, J) are T-ENSCS.

For the case $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) =$

$$A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ we have } \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T \right)(x) \notin$$

$(A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$ because $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$. Again assume that $\beta_{e_i}^T = B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. From this we can write $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ or $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. For this case $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ it is contradiction to the fact that (F, I) and (G, J) are T-ENSCS. And if we take the case $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, we get have $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \notin ((A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$

because $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$. Hence in all the cases $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is an T-ENSCS in X.

Theorem: 3.14

Let $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$ and $(G, J) = \{G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J\}$ be I-ENSCSs in X such that

$$(\lambda_{e_i}^I \wedge \mu_{e_i}^I)(x) \in \begin{cases} \min\{\max\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\}\}, \\ \max\{\min\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\}\} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is also an I-ENSCS

Proof: By similar way to Theorem 3.13, we can obtain the result.

Theorem : 3.15

Let $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$ and $(G, J) = \{G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J\}$ be F-ENSCSs in X such that

$$(\lambda_{e_i}^F \wedge \mu_{e_i}^F)(x) \in \begin{cases} \min\{\max\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\}\}, \\ \max\{\min\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\}\} \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(3.9)$$

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is also an F-ENSCS.

Proof : By similar way to Theorem 3.13, we can obtain the result

Corollary:3.16

Let $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$ and $(G, J) = \{G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J\}$ be ENSCSs in X. Then P-intersection $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is also an ENSCS in X when the conditions (3.7), (3.8) and (3.9) are valid.

Theorem: 3.17

If neutrosophic soft cubic set $(F, I) = \{F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I\}$ and $(G, J) = \{G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J\}$ in X satisfy the following condition

$$\min\{\max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\}\} = (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = \max\{\min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\}\} \dots\dots(11.1)$$

then the $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J)$ is both an T-Internal Neutrosophic Soft Cubic Set and T-External Soft Neutrosophic Cubic Set in X.

Proof: Consider $(F, I) \cap_P (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $I \cap J = C$ where $H(e_i) = F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \wedge_P G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x)\}, (\lambda_{e_i} \wedge \mu_{e_i})(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \cap J$$

where

$F^T(e_i) \wedge_P G^T(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \min\{A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x), (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x)\} : x \in X \rangle : e_i \in I \cap J \}$ satisfy the following condition

For each $e_i \in I \cap J$ Take $\min\left\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\} \right\}$
 $\alpha_{e_i}^T = \min\left\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \right\}$ and $= (\lambda_{e_i}^I \wedge \mu_{e_i}^I)(x)$
 $\beta_{e_i}^T = \max\left\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \right\}$. Then $= \max\left\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+I}(x), B_{e_i}^{-I}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-I}(x), B_{e_i}^{+I}(x)\} \right\} \dots \dots (11.2)$
 $\alpha_{e_i}^T$ is one of $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. Now we

consider $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$, or $A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ only, as the remaining cases are similar to this one. If $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then then the $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is both an I-internal neutrosophic soft cubic set and an I-external soft neutrosophic cubic set in X.

$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, and so $\beta_{e_i}^T = B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ this implies $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = \alpha_{e_i}^T = (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = \beta_{e_i}^T = B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. Thus $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, which implies

that $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$.

Hence $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$

and $(A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x) \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$.

If $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ then $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$,

and so $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) = (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$.

Hence $(\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \notin (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$ and

$(A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^-(x) \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^T \wedge \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq (A_{e_i}^T \cap B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)$.

Consequently we note that $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is both T-internal neutrosophic soft cubic set and T-external soft neutrosophic cubic set in X.

Similarly we have the following theorems
Theorem 3.18
 If neutrosophic soft cubic set $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in I \}$ and

Theorem :3.19
 If neutrosophic soft cubic set $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in I \}$ and $(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in J \}$ in X satisfy the following condition

$\min\left\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\} \right\}$
 $= (\lambda_{e_i}^F \wedge \mu_{e_i}^F)(x)$
 $= \max\left\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+F}(x), B_{e_i}^{-F}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-F}(x), B_{e_i}^{+F}(x)\} \right\}$

$\dots \dots (11.3)$ then the $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is both an F-internal neutrosophic soft cubic set and an F-external soft neutrosophic cubic set in X.

Corollary:3.20
 Let $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in I \}$ and

$(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} : e_i \in I \}$ be NSCSs in X. Then P-intersection $(F, I) \cap_p (G, J)$ is also

an ENSCS and an INSCS in X when the conditions (11.1), (11.2) and (11.3) are valid.

The following example shows that the P-union of T-external neutrosophic soft cubic sets may not be an T-external neutrosophic soft cubic set.

Example 3.21. Let (P, I) and (Q, J) be neutrosophic soft cubic sets in X where $(P, I) = P(e_1) = \{ \langle x, ([0.3, 0.5] [0.2, 0.5] [0.5, 0.7]), (0.8, 0.3, 0.4) \rangle : e_1 \in I \}$ and $(Q, J) = Q(e_1) = \{ \langle x, ([0.7, 0.9] [0.6, 0.8] [0.4, 0.7]), (0.4, 0.7, 0.3) \rangle : e_1 \in J \}$

Then (P, I) and (Q, J) are T-external neutrosophic cubic sets in X and $(P, I) \cup (Q, J) = P \cup Q(e_1)$
 $= \{ \langle x, [(0.7, 0.9][0.6, 0.8][0.5, 0.7], (0.8, 0.7, 0.4) \rangle \}$
 $(P, I) \cup_p (Q, J)$ is not an T-external neutrosophic cubic set in X since
 $(\lambda_{e_1}^T \vee \mu_{e_2}^T)(x) = 0.8 \in (0.7, 0.9) =$
 $\left[\left(A_{e_1}^T \cup B_{e_1}^T \right)^-(x), \left(A_{e_1}^T \cup B_{e_1}^T \right)^+(x) \right]$.
 We consider a condition for the P-union of T-external (resp. I-external and F-external) neutrosophic soft cubic sets to be T-external (resp. I-external and F-external) neutrosophic soft cubic set.

Theorem 3.22

Let

$(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$ and
 $(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$ be

T- ENSCSs in X such that

$$(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \in \left(\begin{array}{l} \max \{ \min \{ A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \}, \min \{ A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \} \}, \\ \min \{ \max \{ A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \}, \max \{ A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \} \} \end{array} \right)$$

.....(12.1)

for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then

$(F, I) \cup_p (G, J)$ is also an T- ENSCS.

Proof:

Consider $(F, I) \cup_p (G, J) = (H, C)$ where $I \cup J = C$ and

$$H(e_i) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} F(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i) & \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J \end{array} \right\}$$

where $H(e_i) = F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i)$ is defined as

$$F(e_i) \vee_p G(e_i) = H(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \max \{ A_{e_i}(x), B_{e_i}(x) \}, (\lambda_{e_i} \vee \mu_{e_i})(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \},$$

where

$$F^T(e_i) \vee_p G^T(e_i) = \{ \langle x, \max \{ A_{e_i}^T(x), B_{e_i}^T(x) \}, (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x), x \in X, e_i \in I \cap J \},$$

If $e_i \in I \cap J$,

$$\alpha_{e_i}^T = \min \left\{ \max \{ A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \}, \max \{ A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \} \right\} \left((A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^+(x) \right) \text{ because}$$

and

$$\beta_{e_i}^T = \max \left\{ \min \{ A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \}, \min \{ A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \} \right\}$$

Then $\alpha_{e_i}^T$ is one of

$A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x), \alpha_{e_i}^T, A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. Now we

consider $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ or $A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, only as the remaining cases are similar to this one.

If $\alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), \text{ and so } \beta_{e_i}^T =$$

$$B_{e_i}^{+T}(x). \text{ Thus } (A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x) = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = \alpha_{e_i}^T$$

$$> (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x). \text{ Hence } (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \notin$$

$$\left((A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^+(x) \right). \text{ If } \alpha_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), \text{ then}$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ and so } \beta_{e_i}^T =$$

$$\max \{ A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \}. \text{ Assume that } \beta_{e_i}^T = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \text{ then}$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$$

$$\leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x). \text{ So from this we can write}$$

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) <$$

$$A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ or } B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) =$$

$$(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x).$$

For the case $B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) <$

$(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ it is contradiction to

the fact that (F, I) and (G, J) are T-ENSCS. For the case

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq$$

$$A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \text{ we have } (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \notin$$

$$\left((A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^+(x) \right) \text{ because}$$

$$(A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x) = A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x).$$

Again assume that $\beta_{e_i}^T = B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$ then $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq$

$$B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq (\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x), \text{ so from}$$

this we can write $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) <$
 $\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$ or $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)$
 $= \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$. For this case
 $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) < \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) < A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$
 it is contradiction to the fact that (F,I) and (G,J) are T-
 ENSCS. And if we take the case $A_{e_i}^{-T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) =$
 $\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) \leq A_{e_i}^{+T}(x) \leq B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)$, we get have
 $\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) \notin$
 $\left((A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x), (A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^+(x)\right)$ because $(A_{e_i}^T \cup B_{e_i}^T)^-(x)$
 $= B_{e_i}^{-T}(x) = \left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x)$. If $e_i \in I - J$ or $e_i \in J - I$, then
 we have trivial result. Hence $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J)$ is an T-
 ENSCS in X.
 Similarly we have the following theorems

Theorem:3.23

Let
 $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$ and
 $(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$ be
 T- ENSCSs in X such that

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) \in \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}, \\ \min\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \} \end{array} \right)$$

.....(12.2)
 for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then
 $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J)$ is also an T- ENSCS.

Theorem :3.24

Let
 $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$ and
 $(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$ be
 T- ENSCSs in X such that

$$\left(\lambda_{e_i}^T \vee \mu_{e_i}^T\right)(x) \in \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{ \min\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \min\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \}, \\ \min\{ \max\{A_{e_i}^{+T}(x), B_{e_i}^{-T}(x)\}, \max\{A_{e_i}^{-T}(x), B_{e_i}^{+T}(x)\} \} \end{array} \right)$$

.....(12.3)
 for all $e_i \in I$ and for all $e_i \in J$ and for all $x \in X$. Then
 $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J)$ is also an T- ENSCS.

Corollary:3.25

Let
 $(F, I) = \{ F(e_i) = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in I \}$ and
 $(G, J) = \{ G(e_i) = \{ \langle x, B_{e_i}(x), \mu_{e_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \mid e_i \in J \}$ be
 ENSCSs in X. Then $(F, I) \cup_P (G, J)$ is also an ENSCS in
 X when the conditions (12.1), (12.2) and (12.3) are valid.

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